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An investigation of fundraising in English primary schools.

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Preface to 2024 publication of thesis

This thesis was submitted in early September 2022, to the MSc Education programme at the University of Southampton. The interviews with participants were conducted in the summer of 2022.

The thesis presented below is the original submission. Where relevant, I have added footnotes to the text to incorporate some of the tutors' feedback for clarity. I am grateful to the tutors for their detailed remarks and suggested enhancements.

Since the submission of the thesis, the topic of school funding has remained newsworthy. Earlier this month, both The Guardian¹ and the BBC² published articles on the financial struggles faced by English schools. The next government therefore faces a considerable task in addressing the pressing issue of underfunding.

¹ <https://www.theguardian.com/education/article/2024/jun/05/eight-in-10-primary-teachers-in-england-spending-own-money-to-help-pupils>

² <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cp991nk1pg9o>

Declaration of Authorship

I confirm that the material contained in this dissertation is all my own work and where the work of others has been drawn upon, it has been properly acknowledged according to appropriate academic conventions. No portion of this work has been submitted or is currently being submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or institute of learning.

Signed: James Hannam

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ASCL – Association of School and College Leaders

CAP – Center for American Progress

CPD – Continuing Professional Development

DfE – Department for Education

IFS – Institute for Fiscal Studies

NGA – National Governance Association

NEU – National Education Union

PTA – Parent and Teacher Association

OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

UK – United Kingdom

US – United States

UNESCO – United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation

UNICEF – United Nations Children’s Fund

Abstract

Due to a decline in government funding since 2010, English primary schools are increasingly required to generate additional income through fundraising. This study generates new knowledge of the issue by investigating fundraising activities at a primary school based in the East of England. It explores the school's income generation strategies, whilst also considering the values and experiences of those involved.

The study adopts a qualitative research approach, incorporating individual interviews, a focus group discussion and documentary analysis. Purposive sampling was employed to select participants with a knowledge of the process, including the headteacher, a governor and several members of the Parent and Teacher Association (PTA). The data analysis approach was influenced by Braun and Clarke's (n.d.) reflexive thematic process, which offers both flexibility and rigour.

The findings demonstrate that current government funding levels for English primary schools are insufficient, thus resulting in an ongoing need for fundraising to reduce pressure on budgets. Those involved in school fundraising hold both positive and negative views of the process, with a notable frustration regarding the lack of government support. Yet despite this dissatisfaction, the social aspect of fundraising is considered to be highly valuable. Unfortunately, not all schools are able to benefit from such related activities, raising concerns about inequality.

The findings generate suggestions for further research on grantmaking, fundraising roles, spending and inequality. With the financial situation likely to worsen in the short term, there is also a requirement for co-ordinated lobbying to further challenge the UK government on current funding levels for English primary schools.

Keywords: education; funding; fundraising; schools

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Context

Government funding for English schools declined by 9% from 2010 to 2020, whilst costs rose (Farquharson et al, 2021). As of the 2023-24 academic year, per-pupil spending is likely to remain 3% below the level of 2010 in real terms (Sibieta, 2022). As a result, many English schools now undertake fundraising activities in order to generate additional income. The purpose of this study is therefore to investigate fundraising activities and their underlying processes with staff and volunteers at an English primary school. The study considers the ways in which the participating school enhances its income, whilst also building an understanding of the experiences, culture and values of the people involved in fundraising activities. Therefore, this study aims to generate new knowledge of the practice, providing new insights into a practice which is increasingly necessary (Body, 2020).

The lack of government funding for education is a global challenge. Despite the high importance that governments ostensibly place on education, research from multiple countries demonstrates that schools do not receive sufficient state support (Alazmi and Al-Kubaisi, 2020; Buys, du Plessis and Mestry, 2020; Good and Nelson, 2020; Winton, 2019a). Scholars have also considered the increasing privatisation and marketisation of state schools in several countries as a result of such funding challenges (Rowe and Perry, 2020a; Yoon, Young and Livingston, 2020; BenDavid-Hadar, Case and Smith, 2018). Researching this topic is therefore important because, despite the economic growth and social benefits associated with global education, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2015) states that the sector is impeded by both funding cuts and financial inequities.

1.2 School fundraising in England

The United Kingdom (UK)'s Fundraising Regulator (2022) defines the practice as that of requesting money, or other assets, for benevolent, philanthropic or charitable purposes. In an educational context, Body, Holman and Hogg (2017) describe fundraising income as monies donated to a school via activities, gifts and grants. Body (2020) explains that staff, pupils, parents and local communities may all be involved in the process of raising money to enhance school budgets.

Fundraising for UK schools dates back many centuries (Body, 2020; Mitch, 2016). Body (2020) suggests that this long history of charitable activities within state-funded schools has generated benefits for staff, pupils, volunteers and the wider community alike. However,

such links have often been required through necessity. In recent decades, there has been an increasing marketisation of the UK education system, overseen by both Conservative and Labour administrations (Body, 2020). The resulting money-saving initiatives required by schools have gradually impacted on important aspects of delivery, such as curriculum breadth, staff workload and SEND provision (Spielman, 2020). Research has also shown that UK schools are increasingly operating in a similar way to charities, providing additional support to vulnerable pupils (Body, 2020; Body and Hogg, 2018). Current education funding policies for English schools are discussed in greater detail in Chapter 2.

School fundraising in England can be broadly separated into four categories: event-based fundraising; charitable grants; donations, and; sales. Body (2020) explains that fundraising can operate directly through the school, or via its Parent and Teacher Association (PTA). Body, Hogg and Holman (2017) make several recommendations that English schools can consider when creating a fundraising strategy. These include: embedding fundraising throughout school activities; investing resources and time in the process; clear messaging; empowering volunteers; building a profile; creating easy donation processes, and; expressing prompt and sincere thanks to donors.

Fundraising events typically include traditional activities such as school fetes, non-uniform days, evening entertainment and challenge events (Body, 2020). Many schools also seek charitable grants or direct donations. Body, Holman and Hogg (2017) note that this process may include seeking potential donors with a link to the school (including parents), or approaching local businesses, philanthropists and grantmaking organisations. Furthermore, Merrick (2020) explains that direct parental contributions are requested by some schools, which are made on a monthly or annual basis.

Schools also generate income by selling second-hand uniforms, school merchandise and food sales (Parentkind, 2022). Seasonal sales of school-branded gifts such as tea towels, bags and mugs can help to boost budgets (Merrick, 2020), whilst competitions and raffles are also popular (Body, 2020). Many schools hire out their site and facilities (Weale, 2017), with some also seconding staff as consultants for other organisations (Creasey, 2018). Merrick (2020) notes that schools may also generate funds via digital means, often through linking to online retailers. He also explains that schools may sell some of their site, such as playing fields. However, this is a rare occurrence and subject to approval from the Department for Education (DfE).

1.3 Spending of fundraised income

English schools typically use the additional income from fundraising to augment their pupils' educational experience, such as the provision of additional facilities, support staff or special events (Body, 2017). Fundraising campaigns often relate to specific projects, such as outdoor play equipment (Merrick, 2020). Other campaigns may link to a single financial objective, which is sometimes reactive in nature. For example, a Nottingham school requested funds to keep its farm running during the Covid-19 pandemic (Reid, 2020). Occasionally, fundraising events are run for other good causes, such as the UK's Children in Need campaign (Body, Lau and Josephidou, 2020). Recent research suggests that fundraised income is increasingly being used to support core school activities (Parentkind, 2021; Body 2020).

1.4 Related advantages and disadvantages

In addition to its main purpose of generating income for a school, other advantages of school fundraising have been identified by international researchers as: enhancing local community engagement (Winton, 2019b; Body, Holman and Hogg, 2017) and introducing children to charitable activities (Body, 2020). Fundraising can also provide an opportunity to develop creative and communication skills (Arantes do Amaral, Petroni and Hess, 2016).

Yet despite such advantages, there are also several negative aspects. Significant fundraising-related challenges such as insufficient government funding, inequality and staff pressure are discussed in more detail in Chapter 2, but researchers have also considered other problems related to the process.

As with any sector, there is potential for fraud and financial mismanagement. Such illegal activities may involve both PTA volunteers (Englund and Martinez, 2015) or school leaders (Miller, 2018). In addition, Merrick (2020) suggests that schools who raise funds via advertising face the risk of a client business generating bad publicity, which could then reflect poorly on the school. Concerns have also been raised by researchers regarding the unhealthy food sold and consumed during some school fundraising activities (Buccino and Whittington-Carter, 2021; Pierkaz-Porter, Lin and Chriqui, 2019; Rowe, Choukri and Horlick, 2019). Similarly, the consumption of alcohol by parents at school events may create difficult situations for school leaders, with Gilligan et al (2020) also noting mixed parental views on the topic.

1.5 Scope of the study

This dissertation predominantly focuses on English primary schools, with the reasoning for this choice detailed in Chapter 3. Due to this specific focus, other important issues such as the funding of secondary schools, private schools and universities are not considered. Although inequality is discussed as a key theme within the literature, there is insufficient space to discuss all potential intersections of demographics such as location, ethnicity, age and socioeconomic status. Furthermore, due to its limited scope, the study does not consider the views of children at the school. Regarding definitions, the term 'school' refers to a state school, unless otherwise noted. The term 'parents' also incorporates guardians and carers.

1.6 Benefits of the study

The study will generate new knowledge because it is one of the few in-depth case studies of primary school fundraising in England. It complements previous similar studies (e.g. Body, 2017) by asking different questions, also taking in to account the many developments in the English education sector in recent years, most notably the impacts of Covid-19 and current inflationary pressures.

In addition to the participating school, a number of stakeholders will benefit from this study's findings and recommendations, including policymakers, researchers and other schools. I plan to publish the study's findings in two formats, to enhance its reach. Firstly, it will be rewritten as a journal article, thus adding to the currently limited literature on fundraising in English schools. The article will provide new findings and analysis for fellow researchers, in addition to recommendations for further scholarship. Secondly, I will produce a short, accessible executive summary document, highlighting key findings and recommendations. This will be shared with educational practitioners, policymakers and charities. This combined approach should result in a wide audience for the study, thus raising awareness of this important issue. Hopefully, the study's findings can then be used to enact positive change, ultimately improving the educational experience of both children and staff in English primary schools.

1.7 Research questions

The study's research questions incorporate suggestions for further research from other studies, most notably Body (2017). The research design process is described in greater detail in Chapter 3.

The central research question is: What fundraising activities are adopted by English primary schools, and what processes contribute to these activities?

The subquestions are: What are the experiences and views of the individuals and groups involved in fundraising activities? How do schools spend the additional income generated by fundraising? How do fundraising processes at English primary schools respond to current education funding policy? And how are fundraising responsibilities delegated? The justification for these questions is also discussed in Chapter 3.

1.8 Outline of the study

This introduction has provided the context of the study, describing the challenge of reduced government funding for English schools which has resulted in the requirement for fundraising. The following chapter considers the detailed literature on school fundraising, demonstrating the global challenges of underfunding and the resulting need to generate additional income. Chapter 3 presents a methodology for studying this issue in greater detail at an English primary school, outlining both the research methods and analytical process used. Findings from the study are presented in relation to the research questions in Chapter 4, with participants' perspectives discussed alongside the literature on school fundraising. Chapter 5 concludes the dissertation, suggesting several potential topics for future research. It also provides recommendations for several stakeholders, including school staff, parents and policymakers.

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Introduction

Much of the peer-reviewed literature on school fundraising is focused on North America. To provide a global overview, this chapter also includes a review of studies from Africa, Asia and Australia. It also incorporates the few studies that have been conducted on English schools. In addition to research by education scholars, the literature on school fundraising also includes legal, sociological, ethical and economic theories. The review therefore considers a wide range of both quantitative and qualitative studies, also referencing education journalism, teacher perspectives and grey literature such as reports by Ofsted and education charities. Overall, three significant themes can be identified within the literature on school fundraising: the impact of neoliberal government policies; the resulting funding inequality between schools, and; the delegation of fundraising roles.

2.2 Neoliberalism

The term 'neoliberalism' can refer to both ideology and government policy. Neoliberal policies suggest that free market principles are suitable for both the public private sectors, thus reducing states' social spending (Winton and Pollock, 2016). Competition within these markets is considered to result in both efficiency and innovation, which advocates of neoliberalism suggest can be applied to the education sector (Winton and Staples, 2022). Neoliberal education policies have theoretical foundations dating from the 1950s (Schaller and Nesbitt, 2020). Winton (2022) states that public-private education partnership policies were notably resurgent as a policy in the 1990s, since becoming globally present. Thus, Yoon and Winton (2020) posit that many such current initiatives are not new, but instead reflect the resurgence of previous ideas and interests.

Winton and Milani (2017) note that neoliberal education discourses position parents as consumers, with responsibility for their children's success in a competitive environment. Such discourses thus promote the view that governments should only be responsible for basic education provision, therefore creating further opportunities to embed marketisation and privatisation. According to Winton and Milani (2017), this policy approach suggests that people who require more than basic state provision should therefore contribute additional funds. Thus, school fundraising could be considered problematic, as it facilitates such

underfunding and effectively shifts part of the responsibility for public education on to pupils' families (Winton, 2019c).

Furthermore, the ongoing usage of school crowdfunding tools, such as the government-backed initiatives Rocket Fund (UK) and Fundraise Yourself (part of the Australian Schools Plus programme), offers more evidence of the gradual shift of responsibility to parents, business donors and the local community. Yet despite the normalisation of fundraising activities, more parents and school leaders are questioning its ongoing requirement (Yoon, Young and Livingston, 2020). Indeed, Yoon and Winton (2020) note that the number of parents donating funds suggests a perception that government funding is currently insufficient. Yet the success of many schools in generating such complementary funds has provided neoliberal policymakers with an argument in favour of such approaches. Ultimately, such successes justify the view that both the private sector and local communities can provide additional support for schools, as the state gradually reduces its role in providing high-quality education (Good and Nelson, 2020; Wong, 2020; Yoon, Young and Livingston, 2020).

2.2.1 Neoliberal education funding policy in the UK

Government funding for English schools is calculated by a national funding formula on a per-pupil basis (GOV.UK, 2022a). Schools also receive additional Pupil Premium payments, which are provided by the government with the intention of raising the academic attainment of disadvantaged children (GOV.UK, 2022b). Most primary schools are also eligible for the government's PE and Sport Premium funding, which provides additional support for physical activities such as swimming lessons (GOV.UK, 2021).

However, Body (2020) explains that it is difficult to provide an accurate overview of school funding in England. Similarly, the Institute for Fiscal Studies (IFS, 2022) states that official statistics do not provide a clear picture of government spending across the various stages of education. Due to the difficulty in gaining accurate figures, Body (2020) notes that both schools and the UK government have employed different statistics to justify their stance. Essentially, schools receive more funding, in absolute terms, than ever before (Body, 2020; Spielman, 2020). However, this statistic is somewhat misleading. In a recent report on school funding, Farquharson et al (2021) state that spending on schools in England (as a share of national income) reduced by 9% from 2010 to 2020, representing the biggest cut to

funding for over 40 years.³ The researchers thus describe the resulting funding squeeze as unprecedented in post-war Britain.

In the UK, neoliberal funding cuts have not been limited to education. In 2010, the Conservative and Liberal Democrat coalition government engaged in a programme of austerity affecting many public services (Harrison, 2021). Thus, the related reductions on community services have had a knock-on effect for UK schools (Body, 2020). Headteachers and governors must now consider the increasing need for additional pastoral support whilst trying to balance an already strained school budget (Spielman, 2020).

Spielman (2020) acknowledges that schools are operating in challenging financial circumstances, noting that costs have risen faster than income since 2015. She notes a decrease in funding since 2010, although provides historical context that funding is 14% higher than the 2003-4 school year. Spielman (2020) also remarks that UK school spending is above average for member countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).

In a recent IFS briefing, Sibieta (2022) acknowledges growth of 7.7% in per-pupil funding for 2022-23, a welcome change of course from the UK government. However, he explains that despite the intention to reverse education spending cuts, school costs (such as staff salaries) are predicted to outpace government projections as of the next academic year. Sibieta (2022) also notes that cost increases will be unequal, with high-cost institutions (such as special schools) facing the highest burden. Ultimately, Sibieta (2022) estimates that as of next year (after factoring in rising costs), per-pupil spending in real terms is likely to be 3% below the 2010 level.

The Covid-19 pandemic has also had a significant impact on school finances, adding to an already stressful situation for staff. Additional costs during the pandemic included investment in online learning, hiring temporary staff, increased cleaning costs and food provision for disadvantaged children (Tobin, 2020). Parentkind (2021) reports that its member associations lost an average of almost £6,000 during the coronavirus restrictions of 2020, totalling more than £75 million. Adams (2021) notes that, although the UK government eventually committed around £5 billion for recovery initiatives, this was well below the £15 billion requested by the education recovery commissioner Sir Kevan Collins, who resigned as a result.

³ A tutor provided a helpful clarification that "the figure of 9% is correct for the reduction in real terms per pupil funding for schools, but not as a proportion of national income" (which is listed in the report as 8%).

2.2.2 Potential solutions

An alternative view on school fundraising is provided by former government advisor Sir Andrew Carter (2018). He remarks that, ultimately, society will decide how to respond to the school funding crisis. This may involve extracurricular activities becoming mandated (thus receiving more government funds), or that society prefers not to pay for such activities with taxes, therefore shifting the burden to parents. The second potential outcome clearly aligns with the current neoliberal education funding approach in England.

Therefore, a key question is why funding cuts have not been challenged more robustly by parents. Indeed, Harrison (2021) suggests that if the public does not challenge such austerity measures, then the government is free to continue such policies, thus generating additional challenges in the future. Harrison (2021) therefore considers the reasons for a lack of engagement, one of which is the government's ideological position that funding cuts are required and therefore unavoidable. Such arguments create an assumption that protesting would not result in success, whilst encouraging others to express support for the policies. Harrison (2021) also suggests that additional barriers have been created by cuts to benefits and social services, thus making life even more difficult for disadvantaged people.

Some of the factors listed above may explain why a parent-led campaign (Fair Funding for All Schools), which gained popularity in the late 2010s, is currently inactive. Similarly, the headteacher-led Worth Less? campaign, which was similarly prominent prior to the pandemic, also appears to have ceased following his retirement. The most prominent current campaign is School Cuts, maintained by the National Education Union (NEU) and supported by several other organisations. The programme's objectives include: the reversal of recent funding cuts; the funding of pay rises, and; additional funds for all age groups and all educational needs (School Cuts, n.d.). The potential for further lobbying is discussed in the conclusion.

2.3 Inequality

Due to the neoliberal government policies described in the previous section, a key concern for researchers is the inequality that can result from schools' reduced budgets. With many schools now required to undertake fundraising activities, several recent studies demonstrate that schools located in affluent areas generate significantly more income than those in poorer areas (Rowe and Perry, 2020a, 2020b; Schaller and Nisbet, 2020; Yoon, Young and Livingston, 2020; Body and Hogg, 2018). Naicker, Inbanathan and Ncokwana (2020)

suggest that Bourdieu's (1986) theory of cultural and social capital can therefore provide a framework for the study of inequalities associated with school fundraising processes. Cultural capital considers an individual's power, status and knowledge, whereas social capital signifies the resources available to someone through being part of a certain group. In practice, parents or staff with high social and cultural capital may benefit from a superior knowledge of the fundraising process and may also gain advantage through networking with specialist personnel or potential donors (Castillo, 2020; Posey-Maddox, Kimelberg and Cucchiara, 2016).

The overall impact of fundraising-related inequality has however been questioned by Guo and Johnson (2017). They argue that the typical activities paid for by fundraising do not directly impact on academic outcomes (e.g. outdoor equipment, trips and guests), although they acknowledge that such activities enhance pupils' overall experience. Guo and Johnson found that the effects of fundraising on educational inequality between schools were relatively small. Although the study only focused on a single district (Toronto, Canada), it raises interesting findings. However, a previous study in the surrounding Ontario province demonstrated a positive relationship between fundraising and achievement, but only for a small number of pupils (Pistiolis, 2012). Given the differing methodologies and results of these studies, similar research would be useful in English schools in order to determine the effects of fundraising on academic attainment.

Although acknowledging the difficulty in establishing accurate figures, the Center for American Progress (CAP, 2017) estimates that PTA fundraising in the United States (US) contributes less than 1% of school spending. However, the organisation adds that much of this additional income is concentrated within affluent areas, further embedding inequality. Interestingly, the DfE (2019) has been keen to emphasise a similar statistic from England, suggesting that only 0.7% of schools' income has been generated by voluntary donations since 2011. Yet given that such statistics appear to contradict much of the literature on fundraising-related inequality discussed in this chapter, independent verifications of the English context would be valuable as part of future research, which is discussed further in the conclusion.

2.3.1 Fundraising-related inequality in the UK

Body (2020) states that a new, ambitious national funding formula for English schools was implemented in 2018, replacing local authority formulae with a single system. Body (2020) explains that the formula introduced new criteria, but did not ultimately increase funding.

Furthermore, Farquharson et al (2021) state that the government's Pupil Premium has not risen in line with inflation since 2015.

Recent findings from Parentkind (2021) show that the average parental donations to schools have increased year-on-year since 2019. Parentkind's (2021) findings also show that certain demographics are more likely to receive donation requests (including younger parents, ethnic minority parents and those living in Northern Ireland and London). Disabled parents, parents of SEND children and those eligible for free school meals were also more likely to have been asked to provide additional funds. Reductions in funding for English schools have also had an unequal impact *within* schools, unfairly affecting disadvantaged children and those with special educational needs (The Guardian, 2019; White, 2019).

An investigation by Guardian journalists Ferguson and McIntyre (2019) found that a top tier of 30 English state schools were receiving millions of pounds per year via donations, whilst others were generating very little. This aligns with previous research by Body and Hogg (2018) which identified several schools as significantly ahead of others, due to their strong philanthropic culture.

Therefore, despite the many benefits associated with school fundraising (and the best intentions of donors), it contributes to inequality in that some children benefit from enhanced educational experiences whereas others miss out. Yet the literature shows that many schools have no option but to engage in the practice to generate additional income, an unfortunate financial situation that has arisen due to several years of insufficient government funding.

2.3.2 Potential solutions

Potential responses to fundraising-related inequalities are considered within the literature. Such notions include government intervention (Schaller and Nesbitt, 2020); redistributive policies within districts (Rowe and Perry, 2020a; Frisch, 2017), increased transparency (CAP, 2017; Frisch, 2017) and a total ban on school fundraising (Winton, 2019a).

Schaller and Nesbitt (2020) explain that several national governments already regulate schools' additional income in order to mitigate potential inequality. They note that the German government prohibits donations being spent on school staff, whereas the UK is slightly less restrictive in allowing additional funds to support non-teaching staff. Spending of school funds by governing boards in South Africa is also limited by law, regardless of income

type (Buys, 2016). Murray (2019) explains that solutions attempted in several US districts include restrictions on parents donating towards staff costs, or approval of excess amounts by a school board.

Several school districts in North America have introduced redistributive legislation to tackle fundraising inequality (Morton, 2021; Schaller and Nisbet, 2020; Winton, 2018). However, van Gelder (2021) explains that the concept of redistribution generates intense reactions from the school community. Whilst some parents appreciate the concept, others express annoyance that money specifically donated to their children's school would be moved to another. Murray (2019) notes that opponents of redistributive practices argue that it can result in knock-on effects, such as a restriction of donations from wealthy parents. She also explains that parents may move their children to different schools or attempt to secede their area from the school district's overview. As such, redistribution initiatives are still rare. Studies have demonstrated that, aside from occasional joint campaigns, additional income generated by fundraising is not usually shared between schools in the same locality (Good and Nelson, 2020; Winton and Milani, 2017). However, the limited joint approaches to date show the potential for a collective system of school fundraising in the future.

Considering the funding context of the Canadian province of Ontario, Winton (2019a) suggests that the only way to effectively reduce the inequities perpetuated by school fundraising is to impose a ban on the practice. This concept has also been discussed (within a US context) by Frisch (2017), who argues that a total ban on private donations would not be a simple process, given the longstanding tradition of community involvement with schools. She therefore suggests that US states should attempt to minimise inequality, but without discouraging voluntary support for public education. Another solution discussed by Frisch is that of limiting the spending of fundraised income to non-core spending, as noted above in the cases of Germany and some US states. Although acknowledging that each proposed solution has both advantages and challenges, Frisch (2017) argues that any of these proposals (or a combination of solutions) would be better than the status quo.

In addition, the CAP (2017) suggests that US states could request greater transparency and reporting of school donations. Frisch (2017) posits that such disclosure could encourage relatively fortunate schools to redirect a portion of their fundraised income to disadvantaged schools. Such a concept could be compared to the UK's annual gender pay gap process, whereby large companies are now obliged to publish data (GOV.UK, 2022c) and often provide an accompanying statement to discuss their gradual progress towards gender parity.

Messit (2015) argues that education will essentially remain inequitable until all schools receive an appropriate level of funding. Similarly, Morton (2021) suggests that debates over school fundraising ultimately distract from the bigger issue of insufficient state support. Therefore, neoliberal funding policies could be considered as the root cause of schools' financial difficulties, with fundraising being used to remedy the situation. As this section has demonstrated, the need to fundraise has resulted in multiple examples of inequality both between and within schools.

2.4 Delegation of roles

Given the challenging financial situation now present in many schools, delegation of fundraising roles has also been the subject of research. This section therefore considers the important role played by staff, parents and governors in the budgeting and fundraising process. In addition to these roles, Merrick (2020) explains that some English primary schools are now employing business managers following budget cuts. This role typically incorporates fundraising tasks, but is not discussed in detail in this review. However, the recent increase in such positions certainly warrants further research, as noted in Chapter 5.

2.4.1 Headteachers

School leaders are increasingly forced to adopt a competitive entrepreneurial approach to fundraising, due to budget reductions (Naicker, Inbanathan and Ncokwana, 2020; Creasey, 2018; Miller, 2018). Miller, Lu and Gearhart (2020) researched the skills required for leaders to generate additional income for schools, finding that problem-solving, interpersonal skills and communication were all considered important. Although such entrepreneurial approaches may benefit school budgets, studies have shown that ongoing fundraising activities can affect school leaders' focus on learning and teaching (Body, 2020; Castillo, 2020; Miller, 2018).

Body (2020) notes that English headteachers spent an average of 10-15% of their time on fundraising, although some reported this to be as high as 50%. Body, Holman and Hogg (2017) suggest that headteacher ideology also has an impact on fundraising, with some opposed to voluntary action (such as fundraising) and others encouraging the practice.

2.4.2 Parents

The literature also considers the motivations and roles of parents involved in the process of school fundraising. Winton (2016) explains that parents are often drawn to the fundraising process, with the practice being considered by many as both a required and desirable activity. Furthermore, Winton (2018) posits that there are many reasons for parental involvement, but a key motivator is the desire to facilitate an educational advantage for their children. Rowe and Perry (2020a) suggest that, despite generating benefits for some students, parental donations to schools nevertheless exacerbate inequalities. Other researchers note that, in addition to this unintentional impact, keen parental involvement in fundraising also leaves government funding cuts unchallenged (Yoon and Winton, 2020). Another potential disadvantage, highlighted by Posey-Maddox (2016), is that parents making more significant donations may feel entitled to a more prominent role in school affairs.

In English schools, parents play a key role in fundraising, both through direct donations and organising activities. Statistics from Parentkind (2021) show that over a third of parents donated to UK schools in the previous academic year, despite the increased financial pressures on households during the Covid-19 pandemic. The research also shows that donation requests from schools are increasingly common, with 45% of parents receiving such messages in 2021 (and 38% contributing). The average parental donation amount has risen in recent years, to a monthly average of £11.62. On this topic, the DfE (2019) state that, when requesting donations, schools should clarify to parents that there is no obligation to contribute. However, how schools respond to the latter advice clearly leaves much room for interpretation.

In addition to direct donations from parents, most UK schools are linked with a PTA group. The primary aim of a PTA is to forge stronger links between school and home, engaging both staff and parents (Body, 2020). Schools in disadvantaged areas are more likely to lead fundraising efforts, whereas PTAs are more likely to oversee fundraising activities in more affluent areas (Body, 2020). Research also shows that women are more involved in the fundraising process (Dale, 2017), creating additional pressures around balancing work with school activities (Littler, 2020; Haley-Lock and Posey-Maddox, 2016). Furthermore, Haley-Lock and Posey-Maddox (2016) suggest that mothers' voluntary work highlights a construct of school engagement as an expansion of caregiving. The current gender imbalance in school fundraising thus warrants future research and is discussed further in Chapter 5.

Parentkind's most recent PTA survey (2022) shows that its member associations generated over £60 million for schools in the academic year 2020-21, down from a pre-pandemic amount of £121 million in 2018-19. However, Parentkind's (2021) research found that most

parents now consider schools' increasing budgetary pressures to have had a negative impact on their child's education.

2.4.3 Governors

Compared to teachers and parents, there is less peer-reviewed literature on the role of governing boards in fundraising. There have been several studies on South African governing boards (Buys, du Plessis and Mestry, 2020; Mestry, 2018) and two studies briefly referring to their role in UK schools (Body and Hogg, 2018; Body, Holman and Hogg, 2017). Content on the fundraising role of UK governors is therefore mostly limited to grey literature such as charity or government reports. This is somewhat surprising given their importance in the school budgeting process. Although they are not directly responsible for fundraising (National Governance Association [NGA], 2021), governors play a key role in schools' financial management.

In the UK, parents take a key role in governing boards, with several positions reserved for parent governors. A joint report by the NGA and Parentkind (2021) suggests that parent governors can contribute valuable knowledge and diverse views to a school board, even though they do not officially represent all parents. Body and Hogg (2018) note that schools can draw on the skills and experience within the governing board, with a governor sometimes acting as the fundraising lead.

2.5 Summary

This literature review demonstrates that neoliberal funding cuts have resulted in a negative impact on global education. These policies have also exacerbated inequalities between both schools and families. Both resulting factors have thus impacted on staff and volunteers at schools, who have adapted their working practices to meet the dual challenge of lower budgets and additional income generation. However, school fundraising in the UK is under-researched (Body, 2017), thus highlighting a gap in the literature. The following chapter therefore describes how this study builds on previous research, in order to generate new knowledge on the topic of fundraising in English primary schools.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I provide detail on the study's methodological approach. I first describe and justify the research design, demonstrating the suitability of the methods used in the study. The chapter then considers the sample selection, research tools, collection instrumentation and analysis process. Finally, I discuss the strengths and limitations of the design.

To recap, the study's main research question is: What fundraising activities are adopted by English primary schools, and what processes contribute to these activities? The related sub-questions are: What are the experiences and views of the individuals and groups involved in fundraising activities? How are fundraising responsibilities delegated? How do fundraising processes at English primary schools respond to current education funding policy? And how do schools spend the additional income generated by fundraising?

3.2 Justification for research questions

The central research question allows for an exploration of both fundraising activities and processes at the school. This question also seeks to ascertain the successes and challenges of the fundraising process, in addition to providing data regarding the associated effects of the practice.

By questioning those involved about their views and experiences, the study generates new knowledge on how the participants both define and interpret their fundraising roles. This aspect of the study aims to discover more about participants' motivations for involvement, in addition to considering the school's overall fundraising culture.

The question regarding delegation aligns with a key theme from the literature. By further exploring this theme with participants, the data will show how related tasks are shared between those involved in the fundraising process. In seeking to answer this question, the study can also ascertain if fundraising impacts on learning and teaching at the school. Data on the skills required for fundraising can also be generated, an important aspect given that previous research found that schools may lack the relevant expertise to engage fully in fundraising (Body, Holman and Hogg, 2017).

Concepts of neoliberalism and inequality, also key themes in the literature review, are covered by the research question regarding the school's response to current education funding policy. Additionally, the fourth sub-question offers the opportunity to discover more about how the school prioritises its spending of additional income, highlighting which educational resources are selected for extra investment.

3.3 Research methods

The research methods were selected with the aim of investigating each of these questions in detail, with the study employing a qualitative methodology. Hammersley (2013, cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018) explains that key elements of this approach include its flexibility, its subjectivity and its emphasis on verbal rather than statistical data. It is therefore a suitable approach for this study, which seeks to discover more about participants' views, experiences and application of meaning.

The research design takes the form of a case study. This approach allows for the collection of multiple forms of data, providing an in-depth investigation of a topic. It is therefore ideal for this project, where the focus is on exploring the activities of a participant group (Creswell and Guetterman, 2020). The case study approach has been used by other school fundraising researchers such as Schaller and Nesbitt (2020) and Body (2017). The overall research design is influenced by Body's (2017) study on English school fundraising, incorporating her suggestions for further research. The study's design also incorporated elements from the qualitative methodology employed by Ofsted (2020), which explored school funding with a range of research tools including interviews and focus groups.

3.4 Participants

Non-probability approaches to sampling are applicable for qualitative research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018) and useful for small-scale studies such as this. Therefore, purposive sampling was used to select both the school and participants. This sampling method is deliberately selective, aiming to reach participants that have knowledge or experience of a particular issue (in this case, school fundraising). Furthermore, although the group may not be representative of England as a whole, the main concern of purposive sampling is to gain in-depth data from participants who are well-suited to the study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

The primary school sector was selected because of its historically centralised fundraising approach, with primaries tending to follow a whole-school approach rather than the subject specific fundraising more common in secondary schools (Edmonds and Gill, 2019). The participating institution was a community primary school, based in a rural location in the East of England. It has been pseudonymised in this study as Oakford Primary School. The percentage of pupils receiving free school meals is slightly below the national average, although participants noted the wide variety of socioeconomic backgrounds of children attending the school.

Within the school, the participant sample was carefully selected based on the important fundraising roles for headteachers, governors and PTAs, as highlighted in the literature. The headteacher's role is of particular interest due to the financial challenges now facing UK schools (Millar, 2022; Ofsted, 2020). Similarly, researchers have highlighted the vital fundraising and financial management role played by school governors (Buys, du Plessis and Mestry, 2020, Body and Hogg, 2018). Scholars have also explored the important role of parent volunteers as part of the PTA (Good and Nelson, 2020; Body, 2017).⁴

The participant sample's combination of knowledge, skills and level of involvement is therefore well-suited to the research aims. The research generates a dataset that provides a thorough response to both the research questions and key concepts discussed in the literature.

3.5 Data collection

The research tools selected for this project are: interviews; a focus group; and documentary analysis. These choices are described and justified below.

3.5.1 Individual interviews

Semi-structured individual interviews were conducted with the headteacher, governor and PTA Chair. Due to the geographical distance between the researcher and participants, the interviews took place via video call. The interviews were both recorded and transcribed. Semi-structured interviews were chosen for their potential to generate both spontaneous and insightful responses. Although the interview and transcription process is time-consuming,

⁴ A tutor noted that I could have also mentioned the limitation of self-selection bias for the PTA volunteer participants.

this flexible method helps to provide a comprehensive understanding of a research topic (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Semi-structured interviews are also well-suited for garnering in-depth individual viewpoints, allowing for follow-up questions if required (Adams, 2015).

3.5.2 Focus group

The original research outline proposed that I would undertake participant PTA meeting observations as a research tool. However, as I was unable to access the school site, an alternative method was required. An online survey for PTA members was considered, but such approaches typically result in a lower response rate (Daikeler, Bošnjak and Lozar Manfreda, 2020). Furthermore, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) explain that focus groups provide a wider coverage of issues than a survey would allow. Therefore, a focus group was deemed to be a suitable data collection method for the PTA participants, given that it could be conducted online. Creswell and Guetterman (2020) note that focus groups offer the additional benefits of being economical on time, with the potential to yield useful data when there is a shared interest amongst the participants.

The focus group included four members of the PTA, aligning with Creswell and Guetterman's (2020) suggestion of four to six participants. The focus group also provided useful variety within the study, providing a useful counterpoint to the semi-structured individual interviews. Krueger and Casey (2009, cited in Creswell and Guetterman, 2020) note that focus groups allow all group members to participate, encourage interaction and provide extensive data. The collective dynamic of a focus group was thus well-suited to the PTA participants, given the association's focus on social activities.

I acted as moderator for the focus groups, facilitating the discussion and ensuring that the conversation remained focused on the questions. I added follow-up questions or asked for more detail where appropriate. A potential disadvantage of a focus group, highlighted by Creswell and Guetterman (2020) is that an individual may dominate the discussion. However, as moderator, I aimed to avoid this by ensuring that quieter members of the group were also encouraged to contribute throughout. The conversation was well-balanced as a result, with helpful insights provided by all four participants. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) also advise that participants may discuss topics with each other, rather than the researcher. However, I was aware of this possibility and kept the conversation on track, whilst still encouraging whole-group participation.

Another concern was the potential for social desirability bias to occur during the focus group conversation, which can affect qualitative studies if participants provide answers that are assumed to be socially acceptable (Bergen and Labonté, 2020). However, given that the PTA members were already familiar with each other, this effect was somewhat mitigated. Participants were also informed that the answers provided would be pseudonymised, further encouraging honest responses.

3.5.3 Documentary analysis

Aligning with other studies on the topic of school fundraising (Good and Nelson, 2020; BenDavid-Hadar, Case and Smith, 2018; Body, 2017), I sought documentation relating to the school's financial management and fundraising activities. As noted by Martin (2018), such additional research provides greater diversity within the dataset. Financial information was therefore selected from credible documentary sources such as the school website, governor newsletters and the UK government's Schools Financial Benchmarking Service (GOV.UK, 2022d). This element of the research provided valuable data on fundraising activities, successful grant applications, school spending and the views of governors. These findings are discussed further in Chapters 4 and 5.

3.6 Collection instrumentation

Interview and focus group schedules for participants were created to ensure the collection of relevant data that would best answer the research questions. Questions were open-ended, with prompts prepared in advance to elicit an appropriate level of detail (DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019). These considerations helped to keep the interviews flowing, whilst also gathering detailed data. I also ensured that the list of questions allowed for a discussion of key themes highlighted in the literature review. The questions were checked for clarity and suitability with the dissertation tutor, before gaining ethical approval from the university. Given the nature of the research topic, sensitive topics were not discussed.

Several questions were inspired by Body's (2017) case study of English schools' fundraising practices. In her suggestion for future research, she posed an important question of whether schools should be expected to fundraise for such supplementary income. This question was asked directly to participants and credited to Body during the interviews and focus group. This was a valuable addition to the schedule, as it often provoked passionate responses from the participants, as shown in later chapters. Another question arising from Body's research was how schools could be supported in generating additional income. This

question was also incorporated, again prompting valuable responses which are mentioned in Chapter 4.

I ensured that these policy-related questions came towards the end, once the interviewee had gained confidence. As these policy questions could potentially be considered as politicised, I followed Adams' (2015) advice to add a precursor comment that the issue had been raised in previous research (in this case by Body, 2017) to therefore encourage honest responses. This, combined with the previous assurance of confidentiality, provided highly valuable data on participants' views and experiences.

3.7 Data analysis

The approach to data analysis was informed by the reflexive thematic approach advocated by Braun and Clarke (n.d.). They note that it is both an accessible and systematic analysis process, with codes gradually building larger themes within a central concept. Its flexible approach means that it can be used across many types and sizes of dataset. It is particularly useful for this qualitative study, given its suitability for research projects that consider participants experiences, views and perspectives (Clarke and Braun, 2017). The authors' six-part process for thematic analysis incorporates: familiarisation; coding; generation of initial themes; thematic development and review; refinement and definition of themes, and finally; writing up the narrative into a coherent whole. However, the authors explain that there may be movement across these phases as part of the process (Braun and Clarke, n.d.).

Following initial organisation of the data, analysis was conducted using the reflexive approach outlined above. It therefore followed an inductive process, whereby both coding and theme identification were driven by the data content. The reflexive thematic analysis approach offers the dual benefit of both rigour and flexibility, gradually building themes and codes through familiarisation with, and re-reading of, the data (Braun and Clarke, n.d.). The process also aided my understanding of how participants applied meaning to their experiences of the school's fundraising processes.

Given the large amount of data generated from the interviews and focus group, I used the NVivo program to aid the coding process. Learning the software offered two key benefits. Firstly, it generated analytical insights that I did not identify during my initial manual coding process. For example, the program generated valuable content regarding the frequency of words used by participants in both the interviews and focus groups, providing another

valuable perspective on the data. Secondly, developing my knowledge of NVivo also provided an excellent professional development opportunity as a researcher.

In order for the project's findings to be both accurate and credible, several validation processes were undertaken (as advised by Creswell and Guetterman, 2020). During the analysis process, I triangulated the datasets, considering the content as a cohesive whole. This integration and comparison of data helped to identify similarities and differences between the participant's responses, thus highlighting any interesting areas of agreement or dissent. Following initial analysis, I also engaged in member checking with a participant to validate my interpretations of the data.

3.8 Strengths and Limitations

Due to the various roles held by the participants, the study was able to shape a detailed overview of the fundraising activities and processes at an English primary school. The project also builds on Body's (2017) case study in several ways. Firstly, it offers a wider perspective by considering the views of a wider number of participants (in this case, governors and PTA members). Secondly, it considers recent developments such as the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and increasingly straitened school finances. Finally, it addresses two important questions that arose from Body's research. Therefore, this study adds to the limited scholarly literature on English school fundraising.

Regarding limitations, the case study only incorporates the views of a small number of participants within a single school. This small-scale study lacks suitably diverse data on how location, demographics, or school structure impact on fundraising. Therefore, the study's findings cannot be considered as representative of the English primary school sector. More research is thus required, the nature of which will be discussed further in Chapter 5.

The original proposal was for the project to take the form of a collective case study of three different school types (local authority, academy and faith). The intention was that by studying these different school types, the project would generate new knowledge about fundraising in varying school structures. However, despite contacting over 40 local schools early in the year, only a few replied with polite declinations. The lack of response from headteachers was likely due to the current challenging situation discussed in Chapter 1, with school leaders facing multiple issues following the Covid-19 pandemic and the recent resumption of Ofsted inspections. Furthermore, given the financial pressures on schools discussed in the literature review, the topic of school budgets may be one that some headteachers would

prefer to avoid at present. In this context, the low response rate is understandable. Fortunately, a school willing to participate was identified in another English region.

Despite these limitations, the study still generates new knowledge of this topic, particularly given that the UK school fundraising has been under-researched (Body, 2017).

3.9 Ethics procedures

The research followed the University of Southampton's standard ethical processes, with project approval granted in February 2022. Following university approval, the school's headteacher then provided gatekeeper permission for the interviews, focus group and documentary analysis. Participants were sent an information sheet in advance, providing context for the study and giving them the opportunity to ask questions prior to their involvement. Written consent was provided by all participants prior to the focus group and interviews. Both the school and participant names were pseudonymised, thus aligning with the ethical processes of similar studies.

3.10 Summary

This chapter has provided an overview of the study's methodology, providing descriptions and justifications for the research design, participant sample selection, research tools, collection instrumentation and analysis process. It has also considered the strengths and limitations of the design. The next chapter demonstrates how this methodological approach generated relevant answers to the research questions.

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

This chapter considers the findings from the interviews, focus group and documentary analysis conducted at an English primary school. Aligning with journal article structures on the topic of school fundraising (Winton, 2019a; Body, 2017), this chapter combines the findings with a discussion of their relation to the literature.

Following a description of the participants, the chapter will discuss their responses to the research questions. Analysis of participant responses will highlight key themes arising from the data, noting any areas of concurrence or divergence with the literature. Other interesting findings beyond those referenced in the literature will also be discussed.

Several themes emerge from the data. Firstly, there is an inherent community focus in the school's fundraising activities. Volunteers are supportive and enjoy giving back to the school and wider community. Fundraising is also intertwined with socialising, thus building networks within and beyond the school community. The second key theme is that of fun and enjoyment, which is an important consideration given the mostly negative discussion of school fundraising in the literature. Thirdly, school fundraising can be considered as a creative practice, generating new ideas in challenging circumstances and also developing a range of skills for those involved. Finally, several aspects of the process are themed as challenges and frustrations, such as time constraints, a lack of volunteers, government funding levels and external perceptions. These themes, their relation to the literature, and their implications for practice, are discussed below within the context of the research questions.

4.2 Participants

As explained in Chapter 3, the study's participants were selected on the basis of previous research showing the important roles that they take in the school fundraising process. Interviews were conducted with the headteacher, a school governor and the Chair of the PTA. A focus group was also conducted with four PTA members. Apart from the headteacher, all participants contribute to the school in a voluntary capacity.

The school has been pseudonymised in this study as Oakford Primary School. Interview participants are also pseudonymised in the text by their role titles. Focus group participants are identified by their participant numbers (P4, P5 and P6). The PTA Chair also took part in the focus group and is therefore referred to by their role title throughout the chapter for consistency. Documentary analysis considered several governor newsletters, the school website and government resources.

4.3 What fundraising activities are adopted by English primary schools, and what processes contribute to these activities?

The school adopts multiple fundraising activities to generate additional income. The overall approach was described by the headteacher as predominantly reactive to “circumstance and need”, rather than employing a specific fundraising strategy. Given the reactive nature of fundraising at the school, the headteacher still noted the importance of clear communication, explaining that campaigns are more successful when the desired outcome is made clear from the outset.

Fundraising activities are shared effectively between the PTA and the governing board, with the headteacher overseeing the entire process. Activities at the school include non-uniform days, raffles, competitions, coffee mornings, second-hand clothing collections, sales of donated uniforms and after-school food sales. The governors are also active in approaching local companies and making grant applications to charitable trusts. Such applications have been made for projects such as library resources and an outdoor learning space, with the latter project also receiving support from a local individual donor. The headteacher said that the school had also received small sponsorship donations from local businesses.

The headteacher explained that the school also offers childcare before and after school. This generated some income but (at the time of the interview) was not self-sustaining financially. The hiring of facilities was also mentioned, but due to the school’s relatively small size, there is limited financial potential compared to schools with larger sites.

In terms of defining the success of each initiative, the headteacher suggested that it was important to consider that financial gain is not the only barometer of success. Large grants generated the most money, but different activities were also described as successful in relation to the positive perceptions of parents (raffles) and children (sponsored events). The headteacher explained that PTA-facilitated events balance fundraising with social activities, an indication of the school’s strong community focus. Similarly, the PTA chair commented

that the benefits of fundraising are not necessarily financial, recalling the children's excitement at recent disco events.

The more challenging fundraising initiatives were the many grant applications that ended in failure (governor) and coffee mornings, which had been sparsely attended in recent months (PTA chair). The Covid-19 pandemic also had a negative impact on fundraising activities at the school, in line with many others nationally (Parentkind, 2022). The headteacher noted that some grant applications had been paused, whilst the governor explained that many grantmakers had directed funds towards specific pandemic-related projects.

Regarding the impact on learning and teaching at the school, the headteacher stated that fundraising activities play an important role in both strengthening the school community and enhancing children's whole educational experience. Although fundraising activities do not directly impact learning and teaching, they still have a positive effect in that they strengthen both the school's identity and a sense of belonging. The headteacher also mentioned the positive impact of fundraised income contributing to a new outdoor learning environment for the staff and pupils to use, which offered more creative and engaging learning experiences.

4.3.1 Discussion and implications for practice

Overall, the school's fundraising activities and other income streams align with the national picture, as described in Chapter 1. The findings also demonstrate the wide range of activities required by a single primary school in order to generate additional income. Although the headteacher suggested that a fundraising strategy is not in place, fundraising still appears to be well co-ordinated at the school. The sharing of fundraising roles between the headteacher, governing board and PTA aligns with good practice highlighted by Body (2017), who suggests that fundraising should be delegated widely to increase the likelihood of generating higher levels of income.

But the school (and others) could consider creating an overarching fundraising strategy. The Association of School and College Leaders (ASCL) and Pebble (2018) suggest that such a plan can help to generate additional income. Specific objectives can then be assigned to either staff or volunteers, which can also help to provide a more effective approach to potential funders such as grantmakers, businesses and the local community. Furthermore, Body, Hogg and Holman (2017) make several recommendations that schools can consider when creating a fundraising strategy, many of which are already in place at Oakford Primary School. These include: embedding fundraising throughout school activities; investing

resources and time in the process; providing clear messaging; empowering volunteers; creating easy donation processes, and; expressing prompt and sincere thanks to donors.

However, given the time constraints and pressures discussed elsewhere in the dissertation, it is unsurprising that many schools may not have time to create such plans. Furthermore, the school's limited options for hiring out its facilities provides an example of inequality, whereby schools fortunate enough to benefit from larger sites can generate significant income through hire fees.

In summary, the findings and literature demonstrate that English primary schools employ multiple fundraising activities to generate additional income. Various processes contribute to these activities, including careful planning, creative thinking, clear communication, and a shared approach to tasks.

4.4 What are the views and experiences of the individuals and groups involved in fundraising activities?

Participants in voluntary roles were asked about their motivations for being involved in school fundraising activities, with the governor answering that their aim was to help the school provide the best possible opportunities for its pupils. Similarly, P4 noted that the PTA offered a chance to help her children, the school and the community. Aligning with remarks by the headteacher, P4 added that fundraising provided enjoyable opportunities for the children, also stating that "it's not all about making money". P5 and P6 also described PTA activities as a pleasant way to engage with the school community whilst simultaneously generating funds.

In addition to income generation, the other potential benefits of fundraising were discussed. The PTA Chair summarised the key elements of the group's fundraising approach as "fun, connectivity [and] community", again aligning with other participants' views on the importance of creating enjoyable activities. The interviewees also described the connections made through fundraising activities as important for both the school community and its wider reputation in the local area. Indeed, there was a strong sense of community across the participants' answers, with a clear sense of contributing to the overall goal of enhancing children's education. Creating memorable experiences for the school community is considered to be of equal importance to generating funds.

In addition to the perceived benefits of fundraising, potential challenges and disadvantages were also raised. As a result of a limited group of people taking on much of the work, there is a notable impact on volunteers' time. The governor described some elements of the process as "mentally exhausting...and demoralising", with the PTA Chair and P4 also noting the considerable time required for the role. However, they also explained that tasks are shared effectively across the PTA team, with P5 adding that time contributions from the PTA were as valuable to the school as additional funds.

A lack of volunteers also impacted the school's fundraising efforts, with all three interviewees noting that a small core group of volunteers took on much of the fundraising work. The PTA Chair explained that encouraging people to take key roles was a difficult process, with P5 agreeing that it was challenging to both recruit and retain members. P6 noted that the perceived time commitment was seen as a notable barrier to entry to joining the PTA, whilst P4 suggested that recruitment could be eased by reassuring potential members that smaller time commitments were welcome. As such, in addition to ongoing face-to-face recruitment efforts, the PTA has a dedicated page on the school website which offers encouragement for parental involvement, again stressing that small time commitments are welcome.

4.4.1 Discussion and implications for practice

Haley-Lock and Posey-Maddox (2016) found similar motivations for involvement in their study of US parents. Such motivations included an awareness of schools' limited resources, demonstrating involvement to their children, building connections and a desire to know more about the school. The school's focus on community fundraising also aligns with findings from Body, Holman and Hogg (2017). In their study, English schools frequently referenced the importance of strong community relationships, with fundraising events used as a way to enhance such connections.

The challenging aspect of time constraints aligns with research in the US by Billingham and Kimelberg (2013), noting that small groups of parents make substantial commitments to school life. Furthermore, Haley-Lock and Posey-Maddox (2016) researched school volunteers in the US, finding notable challenges in balancing work and family life. Those whose employers offered flexibility and paid leave were able to contribute, whereas others encountered barriers due to work demands. Parentkind's (2022) research on UK-based PTAs states that the average time contribution has increased to eight hours per week, equivalent to a working day.

In terms of implications for practice, the PTA Chair's refrain of "fun, connectivity [and] community" is a positive fundraising approach that may transfer well to other English primary schools. After all, if schools are indeed required to generate funds, then they can aim to achieve this goal through enjoyable social activities. Furthermore, time constraints and a lack of volunteers appear to be a challenge in multiple locations. As is the case at Oakford, schools could clarify to parents that participation doesn't necessarily require a significant time commitment. Such messages may help to recruit more members, thus generating stronger community connections and new creative ideas. However, it is clear from both this study and the literature that many parents face significant barriers to school involvement due to either work or family commitments.

In answer to the research question, the views and experiences of those involved in the fundraising process are many and varied. Interpretations of fundraising are dependent on both the school context and the individual's role. In this study, they can be broadly categorised into positive views and experiences regarding fun, community enhancement and making a positive contribution to the school. Conversely, negative aspects of the process include time constraints, a lack of volunteers, adaptation to government funding levels and a lack of external understanding regarding the financial challenges currently facing schools.

4.5 How do schools spend the additional income generated by fundraising?

Before reviewing how fundraised income is spent, it is helpful to consider the context of Oakford's overall income and spending. The school provides transparent financial information on its website, detailing its spending of additional Pupil and Sports Premium funding from the UK government. The current Pupil Premium strategy includes investment in teaching initiatives, staff training, tutoring, family support and other enrichment opportunities. The Sports Premium grant was spent on a range of projects, including membership of a local partnership (offering opportunities for both staff and pupils), equipment purchase, after-school clubs, activity days and the development of outdoor learning.

In addition, Oakford's website provides information on the involvement of the governing board and local authority in the process. The page also links to the government's Schools Financial Benchmarking Service (GOV.UK. 2022d), which provides comparative data

alongside other schools. This data shows that the school is broadly in line with similar institutions on most aspects of its spending (based on 2020-21 figures).⁵

Regarding the spending of fundraised income, the headteacher explained that the outdoor learning space had been the focus of a key campaign run over several years, receiving both donations and grants. Related project costs have included fencing, a fire pit, seating, plants, sheds and bird boxes. The governor noted that PTA funds have been used to cover activities such as pantomime performances or transport for sporting activities, thus reducing Oakford's budgetary pressures somewhat. Enjoyable activities for the children were also important for the PTA, with the group even providing a free ice cream for each pupil on the last day of summer term. Families were invited to bring a picnic to this event, thus strengthening the school community.

The headteacher made an interesting observation that schools should think about how spending of additional income is best approached, noting that the communication of such decisions is important:

...you don't want to be...fundraising for, for instance, extra laptops for the classroom because that feels like it should be something which is within the school budget. So it might be [that we'll] direct the fundraising towards something that is perhaps more attractive, something for the playground, for instance.

The headteacher also noted the importance of informing parents on how fundraised income is spent, to ensure that "they feel that it benefits all of the children in the school." This focus on communication is shared by governors in their newsletters, which provide content on budgeting, recent campaigns, successful grant applications, hiring opportunities and spending (e.g. explaining the value of the new outdoor space for both learning and investment opportunities).

Another interesting finding is that the PTA provides £150 to each class teacher, who then decides how to spend it based on their specific requirements. Teachers have the freedom to spend the money how they wish, though the PTA Chair suggested that the money should ideally provide enhancement to current provision. The headteacher noted that teachers spend the funds in various ways, including class libraries, technology and learning events.

⁵ A tutor commented that this section may have also benefited from excerpts of the school's financial record, to show the percentage of school income generated by fundraising activities.

4.5.1 Discussion and implications for practice

Spending of fundraised income at Oakford again generally aligns with the literature, given the traditional tendency of investing in extracurricular activities (Merrick, 2020; Reid, 2020; Body, 2017). The outdoor learning area clearly brings health and educational benefits, whereas the focus on social events creates memorable experiences for children, families and staff. The school therefore uses its additional income to achieve the maximum benefit. Communication of both campaigns and spending is carefully considered by the headteacher. Such consideration shows the importance of demonstrating to parents that the money is being spent fairly, which is an important aspect of the fundraising process that other primary schools could follow. Such considerations link to Body's (2017) research on English primary schools, which found that successful campaigns are targeted, specific and well-framed.

The equal donation of £150 to each teacher is another interesting approach at Oakford, providing equality across all classes. It is also interesting that Oakford's PTA combines this aspect with larger contributions to other school campaigns, such as the outdoor learning area, demonstrating a diversified approach to investment.

It was important to ask this research question, to ascertain how fundraised income is being spent and how those spending decisions are made. However, it is clear from recent research that the school budgeting process is increasingly challenging (Parentkind, 2021; Body 2020). Using Oakford as an example, income from the PTA and other sources clearly relieves pressure on the school budget, but predominantly supports extra-curricular or enhancement activities. Unfortunately, Shearing (2020) notes that many schools will struggle to deliver such activities (such as school trips) over the next few years, due to core salary budgets being protected. Further detail on the increasingly difficult budgeting process is provided in the following section.

4.6 How do fundraising processes at English primary schools respond to current education funding policy?

All three interviewees were acutely aware of the difficult funding situation for UK schools, stating strongly that schools should not be expected to fundraise for additional income. The headteacher remarked that:

It's frustrating that we've got to a point where, very often, fundraising is actually needed to give us some of the things that we that we should be able to manage within our budget. But the budget is...not there.

In response to Body's (2017) question regarding expectations of fundraising, the headteacher stated that it "absolutely shouldn't be an expectation". Yet without fundraising, they said that Oakford "wouldn't be able to expand on the basic provision" and that the educational experience "would be pared right down...".

It was also clear that government funding has not aligned with increasing costs in recent years, hence the reliance on other sources. The governor commented that:

...I don't think they fully understand the scope of the challenges that schools are facing financially. And it's going to get worse.

... at the end of the day, you're still going out to those parents who are working...are struggling paying their bills.

The governor added that the school budget is currently "extremely tight", necessitating reviews of spending. Aligning with these remarks, a governor newsletter stated that the board had been developing the school budget, considering how best to use the limited funds available. This challenging process was described as a relatively unenjoyable one compared to other governance tasks.

The governor also expressed frustration regarding a lack of understanding from the government, grantmakers and the public about schools' current financial challenges:

...if you're not in education, you don't really understand. And so that leaves a lot of biases and perceptions on what the state fund[s]...So that makes it even more exhausting and time-consuming...and that has a knock-on effect because you're less likely to try. Because the time and effort it takes for the reward...is so low.

As an example of such misconceptions, the governor explained that feedback from a recently rejected grant application suggested that school enhancements "should come from the government or school budget", despite the reality of restricted funds. The governor argued that such outside perceptions must change, partly due to the ever-increasing demands on schools to provide additional pastoral services such as mental health support

for pupils. Ultimately, such spending “has to come from somewhere in the budget, or you have to try and fundraise for it.”

The PTA Chair noted that school budgets are currently restricted, requiring creative approaches to financial management. They also argued that the government should be providing an adequate level of funding, describing the current situation as “very unfair”. Echoing the governor’s comments, they also predicted that the situation would become more difficult given the current inflationary pressures in the UK.

Interestingly, the debate within the PTA focus group was a lengthy and nuanced discussion. In response to Body’s (2017) question on fundraising expectations, P6 noted that:

Ideally, schools would have enough money to run and provide nice things for the children. But we know that that's not true...I don't think you can make a school have a PTA. But I think schools that have them are lucky, because they're likely to get additional things for their children.

An intriguing point was made regarding whether the fun extracurricular activities associated with fundraising would take place if schools were in receipt of sufficient funding. P6 suggested that if the practice were not required, schools may set their own specific uses for the money. Therefore, the concern was that the enjoyable activities currently offered by PTAs could cease as a result of adequate state funding, with the schools prioritising other aspects of provision.

As such, P6 suggested that, even if fundraising were not required, it would still be useful for schools to have a PTA that created extracurricular activities for the children. Relatedly, the PTA Chair also expressed a concern that the education was moving towards an “assessment-driven” system due to funding restrictions, emphasising the importance of pupils’ involvement in sports, drama and other creative activities. The Chair therefore considered part of the PTA’s role as helping the school to address these challenges by providing enjoyable additional activities.

The headteacher and governor also discussed the inequality linked to school fundraising, an aspect which features strongly in the literature. The headteacher was asked about the potential differences between schools. They provided context that their previous educational work experience had been with local authority schools, but suggested that faith schools may:

...have a broader community link, which they can draw on. And I think also very often faith schools will attract a wider proportion of people that are making a distinctive choice. And therefore, might be more prepared and supportive in their giving and supporting fundraising.

But the headteacher also noted that Oakford's status may hold some advantages over multi-academy trusts, due to the "community feel" and "connection" associated with a smaller institution.

When asked about differences in fundraising abilities of different areas and demographics, the headteacher felt that such differences were "inevitable", also referencing the money raised by nearby private schools. They also explained that they had previously worked at a state school in a wealthier area, at which fundraising generated "big, big money".

The governor made an interesting observation regarding the impact of location on fundraising. They explained that the school's rural location meant that they were repeatedly approaching the same small pool of potential donors, lacking the reach of schools in densely populated areas. They also stated that a recent fundraising attempt with local businesses had been unsuccessful. Similarly, the headteacher explained that the many calls on the school community's money can generate an effect described as "giving fatigue". They added that there is occasional stress and tension for some parents, relating to concerns about supporting the school's many fundraising activities.

The headteacher was also asked about the potential for joint fundraising with other schools, a question related to the redistributive policies adopted by some US districts. They noted that some non-fundraising joint events had been held with other schools, which had been a helpful process to both share workload and develop community links. However, in terms of combined fundraising approaches, they predicted that there could be challenges relating to differing school priorities. They added that such an approach would be difficult, given its potential for generating disagreements amongst parents about which school was more engaged and how amounts would be shared.

4.6.1 Discussion and implications for practice

The difficulty of operating with restricted budgets was mentioned by all three interviewees, thus aligning with the literature on insufficient government funding for English schools (Farquharson et al, 2021; Body, 2020; White, 2019). Comments by the governing board in

relation to the challenging budgeting process link to research by Body (2020) which shows that schools are simply unable to manage on current allocations of funding, inevitably resulting in difficult decisions. The governor's remarks about increased pastoral support also connect to research demonstrating that English schools are increasingly providing charitable services in addition to their educational role (Body, 2020; Body and Hogg, 2018).

Regarding the PTA Chair's remarks on a restricted curriculum unenhanced by fundraising, Body (2020) similarly describes the risk of children becoming liable to their school's performance measures. She also argues that such an assessment-driven culture is related to neoliberal policy approaches discussed in the literature review. Spielman (2020) also expresses concern that schools have been cutting both subject offers and extra-curricular activities, thus reducing children's opportunities to enhance their educational experience and develop a cultural awareness. However, it is clear from both the literature and this study that schools have had to make very difficult budgetary decisions, thus affecting provision of certain activities and subjects.

The focus group discussion demonstrated the importance of PTA decision-making, showing the benefits of educational leaders working closely with the wider school community. Thus, in the unlikely event of a fundraising ban (as discussed by Winton, 2019a and Frisch, 2017), there is clearly value in an associated parent or community group that organises enjoyable extracurricular activities.

Remarks by the governor regarding external misunderstandings link with remarks by Breeze (2012, cited in Body, Holman and Hogg, 2017) who states that individuals often do not wish to contribute to causes if they perceive their donation to be a replacement for government funding. The governor suggested that a range of tutorials for the public regarding school funding would enhance understanding, thus facilitating further fundraising.

Yet despite such potential initiatives, the stark short-term reality (highlighted by all three interviewees) is that there are considerable financial difficulties for some families. This unfortunate situation understandably impacts on school fundraising, aligning with Body's (2020) comments that participation in fundraising activities is limited for some. School contributions are likely to be squeezed further given the challenges ahead for many people amidst a severe cost of living crisis.

The headteacher's comments regarding the likely negative response from parents to joint fundraising policies align with the US-based findings of Morton (2021) and Murray (2019).

The rare examples of such approaches to date, and the strong responses that they generate, suggest that they are highly unlikely to become a part of English primary schools' fundraising strategy (unless they are part of a multi-academy trust). However, P4 suggested that it would be helpful for schools to share best practice with others, noting that information shared on successful strategies could therefore be mirrored at other schools. Therefore, in the likely absence of redistributive programmes, there is scope for ongoing informal partnerships between schools in this manner, which could strengthen community relations.

In answer to the research question, English primary schools are struggling to adapt to current education funding policy. It is clear from this study that participants are keenly aware of school funding cuts, but also demonstrate a strong belief that fundraising can be beneficial in many ways beyond generating income. Participants expressed their enjoyment at being involved in the fundraising process, despite its occasional frustrations. This finding suggests that non-monetary benefits may be somewhat overlooked in the literature.

4.7 How are fundraising responsibilities delegated?

Participants talked about their contribution to the fundraising process, also discussing the skills required and their feelings about the role. Interviewees were also asked about the support they received for their role.

To recap on the school's current fundraising structure, the headteacher maintains an overview of the complete process, with the PTA organising most of the school-based activities and several members of the governing board participating in grant applications. The headteacher was keen to praise both the PTA and governing body volunteers for their hard work and valuable contributions to the school. They explained that the present volunteer-based structure is due to limited staff capacity, thus aligning with the national challenge of time pressures for teachers (Ofsted, 2019).

Whilst the headteacher's role is predominantly to maintain an overview and approval of the fundraising process, they also stressed the importance of clear communication (both during and after fundraising campaigns, as explained in a previous section). The headteacher is very supportive of fundraising initiatives, offering advice, providing additional support and delivering communication when necessary. The headteacher described fundraising as always having been "part of the job", but also noted that it is a "really enjoyable" part of the role due to the related "fun and engaging" activities. But they also stated that, despite such benefits:

...there's still a frustration that we need to rely on it. And that sometimes a lot of effort goes in for perhaps little reward.

The governor described her fundraising role as a “driver”, to start up projects and organise them. They noted that the continuous search for funds was both tiring and time-consuming, but considered the highlight of the role to be successful grant applications. They described their reaction to a recent success as “bursting with joy”.

But the governor also noted that their role as a fundraiser was a major time commitment alongside work and family life:

I only have so much time...it's not so much the impact on the school. It's the impact on...my family life. So it's...impacted my family more...it does strain and pull on that.

The PTA Chair described her role as “really fun”, but added that it was occasionally difficult to balance it with other responsibilities during busy times of the year. However, they often emphasised the importance of sharing the work across the PTA members, thus helping to reduce the load during such challenging periods.

Interviewees were also asked about the support they received for their role. The headteacher noted the school community's general willingness to help, but also acknowledged that staff or volunteers may not have the capacity to assist at certain points of the year. The governor mentioned that the board members often share tasks relating to grant applications, whereas the PTA Chair described both the school and fellow volunteers as supportive of her role.

In terms of what would help further, the headteacher suggested that there could be a national organisation which supports school fundraising, but worried that the existence of such a body may further embed fundraising as an expectation for schools. The governor added that grant writing workshops would be useful for schools, given the “trial and error” approach that they had experienced to date.

Participants were also asked about the skills required for successful fundraising. The headteacher described key skills as planning and timetabling, noting the importance of spreading the work to avoid “a constant draw on people's time, energy and money”. The PTA Chair agreed that organisation is highly important, also explaining the need for both

passion and approachability. The governor suggested that networking, communication and teamworking skills are vital, because there should be a combination of those who can create and sell “a vision” with others who can communicate it effectively. In addition, governing board newsletters demonstrate that the board members have undertaken training to enhance their financial skills.

The focus group discussion suggested that a wide range of skills are required for successful fundraising, particularly communication, networking and organisational skills. A knowledge of safeguarding procedures and financial processes was also highlighted as significant, in addition to the need for creativity and design skills. Traits such as determination, resilience, positivity and a willingness to embrace change were also considered as important.

4.7.1 Discussion and implications for practice

The school’s fundraising structure aligns with Body’s (2017) recommendation of an approach involving the whole school. The need for such a wide range of skills shows that school fundraising is highly demanding, requiring significant effort from both staff and volunteers. Oakford therefore makes the most of the skillset of those involved, with a positive approach to generating both new skills and ideas. The fact that many of these skills are contributed by volunteers demonstrates their vital role in English schools, as also highlighted by Body (2020) and Parentkind (2022).

A dedicated fundraising staff member (e.g. business manager) is something that schools could consider, given that Merrick (2020) notes the increasing number of such roles within primary institutions. Providing an example of a primary school employing a full-time fundraiser, Body (2017) found that the postholder managed the Friends’ association, contributed to successful campaigns and built relationships with donors. Such a role could therefore help other schools to relieve the capacity of existing staff and volunteers, although establishing a new position clearly generates a financial cost for schools in the form of an additional salary. There is also an argument that the role shouldn’t need to exist if schools are in receipt of sufficient government funding.

The headteacher’s comment on enjoying the fundraising process somewhat contradicts Miller (2018), whose research found that leaders at English schools considered increased entrepreneurial activity as a significant distraction from leadership. This finding therefore raises interesting questions regarding headteachers’ views on fundraising activities, in that there are likely to be significant variations depending on the context.

The headteacher's comment regarding the possibility of a wider body supporting school funding was an interesting one. As noted in the literature review, the government-backed Rocket Fund already exists to support UK schools, although it is essentially an online crowdfunding platform rather than a dedicated support service. Although such a larger body would be ostensibly supportive, it would bear a similarity with Schools Plus, an Australian organisation which has also received government support. Schools Plus links donors to disadvantaged state schools, which Hogan, Gerrard and Di Gregorio (2022) argue has positioned philanthropy as the solution to disadvantage. Thus, the responsibility for tackling such complex issues is partially shifted from government to schools.

Several articles have discussed the stress on individuals involved in school fundraising, partly due to the considerable level of financial accountability (Buys, du Plessis and Mestry, 2020; Carver, Klein and Gisting, 2015). Thus, schools must ensure that staff and volunteers are well supported, delegating and sharing tasks when possible. Oakford is a good example of such a collective approach, even though the school would appreciate more volunteers to lighten the load. The findings from this study, in addition to the data from Parentkind (2022) show that volunteers contribute a significant amount of time to English schools, alongside their other commitments. Therefore, not only does the government currently benefit from additional funds provided by parents, it also benefits from additional unpaid hours of voluntary work.

In summary, school fundraising is a demanding activity that requires a wide range of skills. At Oakford specifically, those involved clearly enjoy the experience, although the time required can occasionally impact on the personal lives of those involved. Sharing of tasks is therefore a key consideration, in order to avoid an individual or small group being overburdened. Such delegation can be facilitated by a clear structure being in place, ideally involving staff and volunteers and thus providing a strong mutually supportive network within the school community.

4.8 Additional findings

In seeking to answer the research questions, the study also generated additional findings regarding creativity, enjoyment and the role of grantmakers.

4.8.1 Fundraising as a creative practice

This study suggests that creativity is a central element of school fundraising. There is a constant demand for novel ideas when designing or refreshing fundraising activities, in addition to an ongoing need for artwork and design to promote events. It is also clear from the data that PTA members demonstrate a keen openness to new ideas, often generating new concepts collectively. Furthermore, the money generated by fundraising is sometimes used to support creative activities, such as pantomimes and the outdoor learning area. Indeed, the headteacher noted that the new area had already generated creative teaching approaches.

Creativity in school fundraising is not generally discussed in the global literature, with this aspect typically mentioned only briefly (Buys, du Plessis and Mestry, 2020; Arantes do Amaral, Petroni and Hess, 2016). Therefore, this finding contributes new knowledge to the discussion of school fundraising.

4.8.2 Fun and enjoyment

The study's findings demonstrate that fun and enjoyment are key consideration for both the design of fundraising activities and, subsequently, the spending of fundraised income. Indeed, the headteacher described fundraising as one of the most enjoyable aspects of the role. It was clear that the PTA's focus was to create fun, memorable experiences whilst also raising funds. As with creativity, this finding has been mostly overlooked in the literature, although Buys (2016) found that South African schools in her study designed fundraising activities to offer enjoyable experiences for pupils and their families. Implications for English schools could be to consider how fun and enjoyment can form a central part of both their fundraising activities and subsequent spending. This is particularly important given the somewhat distant practice of direct parental donation requests from some schools, as mentioned by Merrick (2020).

4.8.3 Grantmaking

Another interesting finding was the difficulty experienced by volunteers in both researching and applying for charitable grants. The governor deemed grant seeking to be a time-consuming process involving a great deal of research, writing and rejection. There were several reasons for this, including grantmakers' highly varied funding priorities, lengthy application forms and requests for financial quotes in advance. The governor noted that such issues would be off-putting for inexperienced grantseekers.

The governor explained that another “massive challenge” was neither the school nor the PTA being a registered charity, thus affecting grant applications. Regarding the recurring theme of inequality, English private schools are able to register as charities despite protests against this practice (Lowe, 2020). Such registration provides these schools with access to a wider range of funding opportunities.

Yet the school is not alone in its grantseeking challenges. Merrick (2020) notes that, in previous years, schools applying for National Lottery grants were likely to be successful. However due to the current requirement for ongoing fundraising, schools now make applications on a regular basis. The demand for grantmakers’ funds is also likely to increase this year, due to the UK’s cost of living crisis.

Grantseeking is not considered in detail in the UK school fundraising literature, so the findings from this study can benefit both other schools and grantmakers. Regarding feedback for grantmaking organisations, the governor suggested that greater clarity on how to present information would be valuable, noting a strong preference for shorter two-stage applications (a format which grantmakers could adopt to ease the burden on applicants). Grantmakers could also be more flexible on aspects such as advance financial quotes, which may be difficult to obtain in practice. Most importantly, grantmakers should be aware that school budgets are currently limited, so more consideration of educational applications would be welcome. Grantmakers could also consider accepting applications from schools or PTAs without full charitable status, thus addressing concerns about inequality.

4.9 Limitations

Due to the limited sample (six participants within a single school), the study’s findings cannot be considered as representative of English primary schools. Furthermore, due to the study being restricted to a single site, I was unable to collect sufficient data regarding potential inequalities or income differences between different school types, as originally intended. As inequality is a key theme emanating from the literature, a larger sample of multiple schools would improve future iterations of this study. Other recommendations for further scholarship are discussed in the conclusion.

4.10 Summary

This chapter has considered the findings from the study alongside the wide literature on the topic of school fundraising. Areas of concurrence and divergence with the literature have

been discussed, in addition to the presentation of additional interesting findings from the data. The chapter has also considered implications for practice, both for schools and other organisations such as grantmakers. Several potential avenues for further research have also been identified, which are discussed in the following chapter.

Chapter 5: Conclusions

5.1 Summary of key findings

As noted in the previous chapter, the study has achieved the central aim of investigating fundraising activities and their underlying processes at an English primary school. In addition to generating data on activities and income, it has also collected and analysed the views and experiences of those involved. The study has therefore produced new knowledge of fundraising activities at English primary schools, building on previous studies.

To summarise the overall findings from both this study and the literature, schools employ many fundraising activities to generate the additional income now required to balance their budgets. In addition to money, a significant number of volunteer hours are donated to schools each year. The government thus benefits both through charitable donations to schools, and through the unpaid labour of school volunteers. Those involved adopt positive views regarding the social aspect of fundraising, but have also experienced negative aspects of the process such as time constraints and a lack of volunteers.

There is a frustration from school staff and volunteers that government funding levels are insufficient, with fundraised income being used to relieve pressure on budgets. Inadequate funding levels for English primary schools are thus affecting both the curriculum and other educational activities, a situation which is ultimately unsustainable. However, it is clear that Oakford Primary School, like many others, is determined to make the best out of a difficult situation. Although the school is required to fundraise, its staff and volunteers organise fun and memorable activities which enhance the school community. It is clear that there are many benefits associated with the social element of fundraising, aspects of which should be retained in the unlikely event that additional income generation is not required in the future.

5.2 Evaluation of research design

This study has built on the foundations of previous scholarship (e.g. Body, 2017) by following suggestions for additional research and asking new questions. The research design's incorporation of three separate tools resulted in a wide range of data being collected, which was triangulated and checked with a participant for validation. As noted in the previous chapter, the findings are not representative of all English primary schools due to the small sample size. But when the findings are combined with the literature, there is a clear narrative

that schools across the country are required to fundraise for additional income due to challenging financial circumstances.

Yet despite the limited scale of this study, it has generated new findings such as those regarding the role of grantmakers, the enjoyment of participation and the creative aspects of school fundraising. In future, the study could be conducted with more participating institutions, to discover more about the impact of school type and other demographics on fundraising processes. The study has also raised interesting questions that are worthy of future research, as described in the following section.

5.3 Implications for further research

Both the study and literature review have highlighted several aspects of school fundraising which would benefit from further research.

An in-depth study of educational grantmaking, considering the views of both applicants and funders, would generate helpful new knowledge of this important aspect of fundraising. There are also several aspects regarding fundraising roles that warrant further research, including children's perspectives, the current gender imbalance, the growing role of business managers and the barriers to establishing and maintaining a PTA.

Further research is also required regarding the inequality associated with fundraising. Primarily, it is important to independently determine the percentage of English primary schools' income that is generated by fundraising, and how this may be subject to school type and demographics. Scholars could also determine the effect of fundraising on academic attainment in English schools, given the mixed results of Canadian studies (Guo and Johnson, 2017; Pistiolis, 2012). Furthermore, the egalitarian approach adopted by Oakford of providing an equal amount for each class teacher could also be researched, to assess how such a practice compares to making larger donations to wider school campaigns.

Another observation from both this study and the literature is that the definition of 'core' spending is currently unclear. Therefore, it would be helpful for researchers, school leaders and education unions to define exactly what such spending incorporates. Should the definition include only staff costs? Or should it be broadened to include other essentials such as textbooks? These are important considerations, because the current lack of clarity results in a less persuasive case when lobbying the government for additional funds. A clearer definition, incorporating data from multiple schools, would therefore be helpful.

5.4 Recommendations

From the findings summarised above, there are several resulting implications and recommendations for schools, policymakers and parents.

5.4.1 Schools

Firstly, schools should prepare for a difficult few years in which inflationary pressures will be significant (Weale, 2022a). Schools would also benefit from creating a fundraising strategy, both to maximise additional income and delegate tasks effectively. Schools and PTAs could also emphasise, like Oakford, that even small voluntary commitments are welcome, thus lowering a barrier to participation. Finally, by following Oakford's positive approach to fundraising, other schools have the potential to achieve a dual benefit of enhancing the school community whilst also generating funds.

5.4.2 Policymakers

Many stakeholders are calling for additional government funding for English schools, including headteachers (Weale, 2022b), parents (White, 2019) and the many researchers referenced in the literature review. Adams (2022) notes that school leaders acknowledge other government priorities such as energy bills, the NHS and social care. Yet the future cost of not investing in education is significant, given its potential to reduce poverty, address inequalities and contribute to long-lasting development (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation [UNESCO], 2022). Therefore, there is a clear recommendation to the government to support English schools with adequate funding.

The government could also consider changes to charitable status legislation, to bring state schools and PTAs in line with the affordances provided to private schools. As discussed by the CAP (2017) and Frisch (2017) in the US context, the UK government could also insist on greater transparency for school donations as per recent regulation regarding gender pay gaps (GOV.UK, 2022c).

5.4.3 Parents

Both this study and recent accounts from education professionals (Parentkind, 2021; White, 2019) show that many parents are aware of education cuts and their related impact on schools. Therefore, alongside the hard work being put in to fundraising activities, parent

groups could also consider working alongside school staff to challenge current funding levels.

Although campaigns run by teachers and education unions have had some success in challenging the government, parents represent a greater percentage of the electorate. Therefore, a lobbying process involving a wider consortium of parents, education professionals, unions, researchers and membership organisations (such as the NGA and Parentkind) could be highly effective.

5.5 Sharing the findings

The study's findings will be shared through both a journal article and short executive summary, thus providing helpful content for researchers, schools, charities, membership organisations and policymakers. It will add to the limited UK literature on the increasingly important practice of school fundraising. Therefore, the wider communication of this study will contribute to raising awareness of the challenging current situation for English primary schools.

5.6 Concluding statement

Ultimately, school fundraising is a response to a problem. The UK government has created a challenging situation, which school staff, volunteers and parents are doing their best to address, often with their own time and money. This situation is likely to worsen in the short-term, given the anticipated severe impact of rising utility costs and other inflationary pressures (The Economist, 2022; Weale, 2022a; Weale, 2022b).

However, a tipping point appears to have been reached, with several high-profile national news outlets covering schools' financial challenges during the week of this dissertation's completion (Edemariam, 2022; Shearing, 2022; The Economist, 2022). Two former Conservative education ministers and several headteachers have also publicly called for more funds in recent weeks (Weale, 2022a; Weale, 2022b). These comments add to the concerned remarks from Ofsted's chief inspector regarding cuts to the curriculum (Spielman, 2020). In addition to the IFS report (Farquharson et al, 2021) on the unprecedented level of funding cuts, findings from Parentkind (2021) also demonstrate displeasure from parents. Therefore, with such a large body of evidence, it is clear that the UK government should considerably increase its support for English primary schools. If schools continue to be

underfunded, the educational and societal repercussions will be both significant and long-lasting.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview schedule for headteacher

1. Does the school have an overall fundraising strategy? If so, what is it?
2. What fundraising methods do you use to generate additional income for the school?
3. Do you perceive any other benefits to the fundraising process other than generating money?
4. Conversely, does the fundraising process have any negative knock-on effects?
5. What have been your most successful fundraising strategies to date?
6. Conversely, what challenges has your school faced in generating additional funds?
7. How have your fundraising practices changed during the Covid-19 pandemic? And what has been the impact of these changes?
8. What skills do you think are required for successful fundraising?
9. What support do you receive in your fundraising role?
10. How does fundraising impact on learning and teaching?
11. Aside from fundraising, how else does the school generate additional income?
12. Of the additional fundraised income, what is it spent on?
13. If you stopped fundraising, how would it impact your annual budget?
14. How does your school status (e.g. faith, free, LA, academy) inform your fundraising strategy?
15. How are the fundraising activities shared or delegated at the school? And why do you use this system?
16. How would you describe your role within the school fundraising process? And how do you feel about that role?
17. Researcher Alison Body (2017) asks if schools should be expected to fundraise for additional income. What are your thoughts on this?
18. Body (2017) also asks how schools can be best supported in achieving their fundraising objectives. Therefore, what would help you and your school to fundraise more successfully?
19. Many academic studies report that schools situated in wealthy areas receive significantly more financial support than those in poorer locations. What is your view on this?
20. Have you considered joint fundraising with other schools? What may be the benefits and challenges of this approach?

Appendix 2: Interview schedule for governor

1. What are your main motivations for being involved in raising funds for the school?
2. What fundraising methods do you use to generate additional income for the school?
3. Do you perceive any other benefits to the fundraising process other than generating money?
4. Conversely, does the fundraising process have any negative knock-on effects?
5. What have been your most successful fundraising strategies to date?
6. Conversely, what challenges has your school faced in generating additional funds?
7. What skills do you think are required for successful fundraising?
8. How would you describe your role within the school fundraising process? And how do you feel about that role?
9. How does the time spent on fundraising impact your main role at the school?
10. What support do you receive in your fundraising role?
11. Researcher Alison Body (2017) asks if schools should be expected to fundraise for additional income. What are your thoughts on this?
12. Body (2017) also asks how schools can be best supported in achieving their fundraising objectives. Therefore, what would help you and your school to fundraise more successfully?

Appendix 3: Interview schedule for PTA Chair

1. What fundraising methods do you use to generate additional income for the school?
2. What are your main motivations for being involved in raising funds for the school?
3. What have been your most successful PTA fundraising campaigns to date?
4. Conversely, what challenges has the PTA faced in generating additional funds?
5. How have your fundraising practices changed during the Covid-19 pandemic? And what has been the impact of these changes?
6. Of the additional fundraised income, does the PTA have a say on how the money is spent?
7. What is the most enjoyable aspect of the fundraising process?
8. Do you perceive any other benefits to the fundraising process other than generating money?
9. Conversely, what is the most difficult aspect?
10. What skills do you think are required for successful fundraising?

11. How would you describe your role within the school fundraising process? And how do you feel about that role?
12. What support do you receive in your fundraising role?
13. Researcher Alison Body (2017) asks if schools should be expected to fundraise for additional income. What are your thoughts on this?

Appendix 4: Focus group schedule for PTA participants

1. What are your main motivations for being involved in raising funds for the school?
2. What is the most enjoyable aspect of the fundraising process?
3. Conversely, what is the most difficult aspect?
4. What skills do you think are required for successful fundraising?
5. Researcher Alison Body (2017) asks if schools should be expected to fundraise for additional income. What are your thoughts on this?